

THE ROLE OF FEMINISM IN INDIAN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

When studying in women in Indian Society, there is a contradiction with regard to their social status. Religious glory is given on one side & on the other side is actually given the secondary & lower position. In our Indian society the equation is "Woman means suffering & suffering means woman." Men's dominated society always provided a secondary place (status) for women. No Matter how much she develops, this society does not allow her to rise, even today this truth can't be denied. Feminism is the fight for women to be equated with men. It's an attempt to get what she has not received for many years.

KEYWORDS: Indian society, Women, Feminism.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To observe situation & changing women's role in Indian society.
- 2) Explain the meaning of feminism.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is presented is the based on secondary sources information on various books & websites related to women & feminism is included.

INTRODUCTION

Observing from ancient times it seems that there have been many changes in the situation & role of women was created in the mail- dominated culture and gradually women's rights began to decline. It was then that feminism was born. In the mail- dominated society a woman is a commodity that migrates from one house to another, often sold in the name of dowry. Therefore it is imperative for women in Indian society to consider feminism in that regard.

DISCUSSION

The life of women in Indian society seem to be a very fragile subject. A great deal of misery when it comes to their lives. In fact it was suffering, they didn't dare to say in a little word. Their word was

gripped with sorrow. Getting out of this is not difficult but impossible.

Ancient period (Vedic period) & women's Location (status):

In ancient India there seems to be feminine culture. When considering ancient women. They had a valuable place in social, economic & political life. The women of the Vedas attain high status. The Vedas used to be the emperor of the house. They had no restrictions. The women of the Vedic period had had the freedom of war. In the battlefield from study teaching. Such as Apala, Ghosha, Aditi, Dakshayani, Surya, Lopmudra, Gargi, Maitryee.

The following are some of the rights of women in Vedic times:

- ❖ Women had had rights to form their own army – Yajurved 17.45
- ❖ Right to take part in war. – Yajurved 17.45
- ❖ Court rights – Yajurved 10.26
- ❖ Marriage allowed after celibacy methodical study – Athrwaved 11.5.8
- ❖ Only send daughter in the law with intelligence & education that was the tradition of giving knowledge. – Athrwaved 14.1.6

- ❖ Girls had the rights to use her own knowledge in her low's house. – Athrwaved 14.1.20
- ❖ They had rights to express their own opinion in public events. – Athrwaved 12.3.52
- ❖ Girls had equal rights in property – Rugved 3.31.1

This shows that the position of women in society was high. It appears that women were equal with men in each field.

The Medieval Period:

In medieval period the culture seemed predominantly male. In medieval times women were given secondary positions. There were the problem of injustice, oppression & exploitation of women, such as Satipratha, Keshmudan, Devdasi, Female Feticide. They were lived in a deplorable & terrible condition. They had no rights to acquire knowledge.

Women's Movements & Law's :

In medieval period there were some social worker who realized the harsh condition of women & took the decision to change that scenario. That created a lot movement. Such as "Bhart Mahila Parishad, Bhartiya Stri Mahamandal, Women's Indian Association, All India Women's conference" this organizations made women aware of their rights. In fact they realized that they existed independently. Satibandi law (1829), Widow remarriage legal recognition (1856), Female feticide prevention (1870), Inter-cast marriage recognition (1872), Voting rights for women (1921), Child marriage law (1929), Property rights for women (1937), Anti-abortion law (1988). This important laws has created a special awareness among women. Savitribai Fule, Jotiba Fule, Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Keshv Karve had an important role in this social cause.

Post-Independence Period & Feminism :

The expected outcome of the movement in the medieval period was simply "Women's Empowerment." In which women became aware of their total rights. Today women are working with men in every field. In fact in many fields have made remarkable achievements by providing their special talents & it has created a new world.

The Concept of feminism:

The Concept of feminism involves changing the deeply rooted practices of society & making women aware of their existence. They are also expected to realize their devaluation & exploitation.

"Feminism is awareness of women's oppression & within the family & conscious action by women & men to change this situation."

"Feminism is a new chapter in women's history, a new idea, a new vision, a new dream, a new direction."

In the view of above definition the following as aspects are seen:

- 1) Feminism describes change in the individual & expectations of change in society.
- 2) The Feminism concept answers basic questions.
- 3) Feminism compels the analysis of the males dominated society.
- 4) Feminism promotes equality for women.
- 5) Feminism proves that a woman is no less than a man in any field.
- 6) Feminism demands economic, social, political independence.
- 7) Feminism are not anti-masculine.
- 8) Feminism is not a conflict, but an infected state.
- 9) Feminism involves the idea of manhood.
- 10) Feminism is a transformational consciousness.

CONCLUSION

For thousands of years our Indian society had two side thinking above women on one side they worship the women on the name of Goddess, on the other hand they treated her worse than animals. The constitution was also amended to give women exclusive rights. Feminism is group of many movements & ideologies that define, prove, demand equality for women. It is the flow of gender discrimination toward men & women. It is a social & political awareness for women. It is the platform to step out & assert own rights. Feminism is the key for equal opportunity. When feminism covers the entire universe a new world be created. Many movements, seminars, conferences, workshop have tried to change the positions of women in our society but the aim of feminism cannot be achieved until or unless women herself not understand her own important & position in society.

REFERENCE

1. Loksatta, News Paper.
2. vkpk;Z cynso mik/;k; % oSfnd lkfgR; vkSj laL—rh] "kkjnk laFkku okjk.klh 1998
3. fyax vkSj fodkl ds eq | s % lqxrk eksqarh] 1998
4. Feminist theory & knowledge : fizrh deZdkj] 1998
5. Feminism & handbook for teachers : Sharmila Rege, 2005
6. <http://feminisminindia.com>.